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“SANDRO FIDEL”

Hailing Alexandros, charming and prayed
Known to be defender of men
Loyalty is a need
Newest hero, everyone is thrilled

Beyond words, heaven knows
How this name is prayed the most
His name is well-thought of
God sends emerging thoughts

Between the lines
Sandro Fidel comes to mind
That despite of being left most of the times, due to his parents working hard
That he'll grow God-fearing, healthy, friendly, and kind

Sandro as defender of men
Faithful and humane
Fidel, as loyal steward
That as he grows, he'll be loving the life, he ever wanted to.